

Synthetic controls for diverse biomedical applicability scenarios

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Synthetic controls refer to the precise manipulation of size, shape, composition, surface chemistry, and certain properties during fabrication. This level of control is crucial for tailoring nanostructures for specific applications in various fields, including biomedicine, catalysis, electronics, and environmental remediation. Magnetic nanostructures hold tremendous promise in the field of biomedicine due to their unique properties and versatile applications such as drug Delivery, Hyperthermia Therapy, Imaging, Biosensing, Cell Labeling and Tracking, Tissue Engineering and Detoxification.

Continued advancements in synthetic methodologies and characterization techniques are driving the development of increasingly sophisticated nanoparticle-based materials with enhanced performance and functionality. Specifically, for magnetic nanostructures, key aspects correspond to tuning their magnetism following approaches to:

1. **Control Size:** By controlling the size distribution of nanoparticles during synthesis, researchers can tune their magnetic properties.
2. **Control Composition:** Varying the composition of magnetic nanoparticles can significantly influence their magnetic behavior i.e. magnetic moment, magnetic anisotropy, and Curie temperature of nanoparticles.
3. **Modify Surface:** Can shield nanoparticles from agglomeration or specifically target biomedical probes.
4. **Control Shape:** The shape of nanoparticles also plays a critical role in determining their magnetic properties by adjusting the aspect ratio or geometry of the nanoparticles.
5. **Multi-functionalize Nanocomposites:** Incorporating magnetic nanoparticles into composite materials or hybrid structures with other functional materials (e.g., polymers, metals, ceramics) can lead to synergistic effects and tailored magnetic, electrical, and mechanical properties.
6. **Engineer Nanostructures:** Fabricating complex nanostructures (e.g., core-shell nanoparticles, heterostructures) allows for precise control over the magnetic interactions between different components, leading to enhanced magnetic properties and functionalities.

In this talk, I will present case studies of magnetic nanoparticle-based systems synthesized by Chemical Co-precipitation, Thermal Decomposition, Hydrothermal/Solvothermal Synthesis and Solid-State Pyrolysis and corresponding synthetic controls to produce nanostructures with controlled size, composition, morphology, and certain biomedical functionalities.